
A Phenomenology of the Learning Journey of Graduates of the Master of Arts in Teaching Filipino of Two Universities in the Province of Bohol

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ABSTRACT

The standards implemented by the Commission on Higher Education for graduate schools are contained in a seemingly capsulized set of descriptors such as better knowledge and skills and lifelong learning. Considering the criteria above, this study aimed to explore the transformation of students in terms of their knowledge and skills, shaped by their social contexts, through their experiences in the Master of Arts in Teaching Filipino program. The research is based on interviews with 12 graduates from two universities in Bohol. According to transformative learning theory, professionals experience a sense of disorientation that motivates them to thoroughly examine their knowledge, skills, and practices, ultimately leading to generalizations that deepen their understanding of their experiences. From the responses of the participants, it can be said that their pedagogical knowledge and skills, subject content and the 21st century, and the social context such as equipment and facilities, colleagues and collaborators, and curriculum have helped in their personal and professional transformation. However, they also had disorientations that made them aware of the reality of their profession, the education system, and the society they live in. Therefore, it can be said that although the two universities are effective partners in the students' learning journey, there is still room for enhancement in their approach to fostering meaningful development.

Keywords: Disorientation, professional development, transformative learning, transformation, CHED descriptors

INTRODUCTION

This study reflects the researcher's advocacy. With over a decade of experience teaching in the master's program in Teaching Filipino, the researcher carefully selects practices and approaches for each course every semester, driven by the continuous pursuit of the most effective teaching method. Efforts are made to continuously refine methods with the goal of shaping the ideal graduate profile for the program aligned with the new Policies, Standards, and Guidelines (PSG) of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), which emphasize these descriptors, particularly the development of advanced knowledge and skills, self-directed research, and lifelong learning, self-direction/leadership, and high substantial degree of independence.

Buenvinida and Yazon (2017) confirmed in their research that graduate studies are a way to improve the skills and abilities of professional teachers in the performance of their teaching duties, improving the capacity of students, and managing learning programs. In fact, this is what prompted the researcher to determine which knowledge and skills were meaningful to the students taught and the classroom work. It is also important to prove that the standards and learning opportunities in graduate studies have helped shape an individual undergoing professional development.

Professional development is an aspiration that may be personally motivated or prompted by a job or career need. To achieve this, it is necessary to promote it under the supervision of other professionals within an institution. However, mature and professional students have experiences in their schooling and outside of schooling that are more appropriate to their age and more beneficial to their transformation.

Derived from Mezirow's (1978) Transformational Learning, based on the study of women who returned to work after several years of family care, learning depends not only on

information and skills but on changing beliefs. According to Mezirow, it is a process of reinterpreting the prior perspective as a guide to the future (Dochy et al., 2011). Gordon (2003) and DeAngelis (2019) identified that the center of transformational learning is a disorienting dilemma. DeAngelis described that a person becomes aware of the impact of his beliefs, thoughts, and actions on his identity. However, the impact is not the same for each individual. As one grows older, some problems cannot be solved immediately and require careful analysis—a process in which a person discovers aspects that need to be replaced, changed, or focused in a different direction.

On the other hand, this timely influence of Descriptor 7 from the PSG of CHED and the Sustainable Development Goals and the priority action areas such as transforming learning environments and building capacities of educators, according to Glavič (2020) is focused on empowering teachers to change themselves and society while that has to do with advanced knowledge and skills in the specialized field of training, self-directed research, lifelong learning and the application of aforementioned professional skills and creative writing.

Therefore, this research aims to obtain a picture of the transformation of the graduates of the Master of Arts in Teaching Filipino in the universities of the province of Bohol in relation to their learning experiences and the practice of their profession. Specifically, it intends to identify the transformations that occurred in the individual graduates after self-evaluation and critical assessment of inferences about knowledge and skills in their role performance as Teacher, Community member, Researcher, Author or writer, and Institution/school administrator. Eventually, the conducted research will help to contribute a new perspective and methods to the teaching of professors with the help of culturally transformative improvement methods.

METHODOLOGY

This study is qualitative research based on a phenomenological approach with the purpose of discovering the

"disorienting dilemma" of the graduates of Master of Arts in Teaching Filipino at two universities in the province of Bohol in relation to their performance of their duties. In accordance with Heidegger's hermeneutic phenomenology mentioned in Randall's (2014) study, the data analysis of Van Manen includes interviewing respondents with similar experiences data analysis using transcription codes, including the researcher's reflections while undergoing data collection and analysis. The data analysis made use of thematic analysis. The sample came from teachers who graduated with a Master of Arts in Teaching Filipino in the Academic Year 2015-2021 from two universities in the province of Bohol. Data were analyzed according to stages: first: Clarification of Views, second: Lived Experiences, and third: Limiting Lived Experience-Structural Stage; Fourth: Writing about Limiting Lived Experience with Integration of Specific Structures into General Structures. In relation to the conflict of interest, the researcher ensures that there is no personal relationship with any agency. There is no favor or benefit to any party, whether researcher, participant, or third party, except to present clear and objective results. It was also ensured that the participants read and signed the informed consent form, the freedom to withdraw or stop participating and that there was no implied harm in their participation. There is also no implication of the data collected on the state or honor of the university involved in the research. Its purpose is to develop the teaching method at the graduate level, especially in the Master of Art in Teaching Filipino program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In general, the teachers' transformation from their learning journey was positive. All of them realized that their studies in graduate school under the Master of Arts in Teaching Filipino or MAT-FIL contributed to their development in skills and knowledge for their role performance either as a teacher, community member, researcher, author or writer, and institution or school administrator. However, there are also surprising and surprising disorientations. It can be found in the lower part after discussing the different transformations

according to the performance of the different roles of the participants.

Similar to the second problem, the answers of the participants were sorted, and sub-themes were identified. Sub-themes can be grouped into two: Personal Transformation and Professional Transformation in their role performance as a teacher, community member, researcher, author or writer, and institution or school administrator.

Teacher. It was as a teacher that the participants realized the **personal transformation**, and some expressed that they became more prepared in the physical and mental aspects. Teacher 4 and Teacher 7 indicated self-confidence. For Teacher 4, their graduate studies opened them up to pursue post-graduate studies. For Teacher 7, they gained self-confidence in teaching Filipino at the secondary and tertiary levels. This is also the reason for Teacher 11 to be confident and creative in teaching.

For Teacher 10, the lesson "Alegorya sa Yungib" (Allegory of the Cave), written by Plato, served as a mirror to their experience, which indicated that they needed to see reality in order to understand what they should do. Teacher 1 also said that experiences are a big contribution because not everything is learned in the classroom.

Their experiences in their teaching careers shaped the teachers' professional transformation. Through their graduate studies, Teacher 3 learned to adapt and integrate modern teaching methods using technology. Similarly, Teacher 5 realized the importance of diversifying creative activities to keep students engaged and prevent boredom. In line with this, Teacher 10 consistently emphasized the need to take things slowly and adjust to the students and their needs.

Member of the Community. As a member of the community, the transformation as a teacher of the participants was confirmed in their experiences after their analysis and assessment of the inferences related to their performance in the role.

In their **transformation**, Teacher 1 realized that his social and spiritual aspects related to community work had expanded. Similar to Teacher 1, Teacher 2 experienced an expansion in his social aspect. From being shy, he now knows how to keep up and participate in community activities.

Teacher 7 says that their transformation is their awareness of the cultures and traditions of their community. According to them, "*Higit na nagkaroon ako ng kamalayan sa mga kultura at tradisyon sa aming pamayanan at bukas din sa aking isipan na tangkilikin ang ibat ibang sining sa bansa.*" [I became more aware of the cultures and traditions in our community, and I am also open to enjoying different arts in the country.] The transformation of Teacher 7 is also related to his recognition that the culture of the country is rich, and it is only necessary to explore it.

The personal transformation of Teacher 1 and Teacher 2 is in their interaction with their community. Therefore, the teacher's constant knowledge and interaction with the community he belongs to as a professional is necessary.

In the **professional transformation**, Teacher 4 said that it is expected to 'level up' because the level has already been reached. Teacher 6 appreciated how to communicate. Teacher 8 focused on new information and valued information from his graduate and post-graduate teaching.

Teacher 3 had experience working outside the teaching profession. However, they were surprised by the additional responsibilities assigned to them. They shared: "*Nakuratan pod ko nga ingon ana diay ang set-up—aside from purely focusing on teaching, lessons, and competencies, there are still other tasks...*" ["I was surprised that the set-up is like that—aside from solely focusing on teaching, lessons, and competencies, there are still other responsibilities..."]

Teacher 8, on the other hand, experienced a transformation in their profession through their teaching journey in a rural town in Bohol. They had to adjust their expectations to understand the realities faced by students who were often absent—not out of neglect, but because they needed

to help their families. This realization became clear through their continuous reflection:

"Before, bata pa kami, pumupunta kami dito, hindi ko naa-appreciate ang lugar na ito kasi kapag pumupunta kami sa bahay ng lola ko, wala talagang ilaw, puro bukid. Walang tindahan, tapos pakiramdam ko sobrang layo ng Danao. Pero nang binigyan ako ng item... okay lang naman dahil lugar ito ng mama ko. Parang doon ko na lang na-appreciate at na-differentiate ang lifestyle ng mga bata sa Tagbilaran at dito. Kapag may batang nagsabi, 'Ma'am, puwede bang mag-absent kami? Kailangan po naming mag-ani,' dati parang nagagalit pa ako. *'Ha? Kailangan bang ikaw mismo ang nandoon?'* Pero habang tumatagal, mas nakita ko ang hirap ng buhay nila. Napagtanto ko na kailangan talaga nating pahalagahan ang ganitong mga bata, kasi pagkatapos nilang mag-ani, minsan makikita mong nagmamadali pa silang pumasok sa paaralan. Kailangan lang talaga nilang mag-absent, kasi kung hindi, wala silang makakain. Mas naintindihan ko ngayon ang kahalagahan ng sinasabi nilang pagpapababa ng standard—hindi para pababain ang kalidad ng edukasyon, kundi upang maunawaan ang tunay na kalagayan ng mga estudyante."*

[Before, when I was young, we used to come here, but I didn't appreciate this place. When we visited my grandmother's house, there was no electricity—just fields everywhere. There were no stores, and I felt like Danao was so far away. But when I was assigned here, I realized it was my mother's hometown, and that's when I started appreciating and understanding the difference in lifestyles between children in Tagbilaran and those here. When students ask, 'Ma'am, can we be absent? We need to help with the harvest,' I used to get frustrated. *'Why do you have to be the one there?'* But over time, I saw how difficult their situation was. I learned to appreciate their struggles because, after the harvest, I would see them rushing to school. They needed to be absent—not out of

laziness, but because if they didn't help, their families wouldn't have anything to eat. That's when I truly understood what it means to lower our standards—not to compromise learning, but to meet students where they are and recognize their realities.]

This experience deepened Teacher 8's appreciation for the resilience and determination of their students, reshaping their perspective on education and compassion in teaching.

It is evident that only a few teachers explicitly recognized their direct relationship with the community when sharing their experiences. Despite this, the insights they gained in their roles as community members are remarkable. The limited instances of teachers discussing their experiences in relation to their community involvement should not be seen as a weakness of the research. In fact, when asked, participants openly acknowledged that they did not perceive a strong or visible connection with their community, as exemplified by Teacher 11's statement. This suggests that the structural format and questioning method of the study may have influenced their responses, which can be considered a limitation of the research.

The researcher's analysis of related literature, particularly Bourn (2016), supports this perspective: "*Teaching has always been seen as more than just another profession or job.*" Similarly, Hansen described teaching as a "*moral practice.*" At the same time, Fullan emphasized that "*scratch a good teacher, and you will find a moral purpose.*" This evolving moral purpose shapes teachers' methods and approaches, guiding them toward fulfilling their role not just as educators but as influencers of positive change. Teachers play a crucial role in sharing their values and perspectives with students, motivating them to learn and actively participate in society. At the same time, they must also refine their understanding of their personal and professional development needs.

In light of Bourn's observations and the participants' experiences, it can be inferred that even if some teachers did not explicitly express their transformation as members of the community, the impact of their role is deeply embedded in their hearts.

Researcher

Similar to the previously discussed roles, the participants realized that their transformation is linked to both **personal transformation** and **professional transformation**, which serve as the thematic framework for the following analyses.

Regarding **personal transformation**, Teacher 2 reflected on their experiences as a researcher while pursuing a Master of Arts degree in graduate school. They acknowledged the challenge of balancing work and academic responsibilities, even managing to attend seminars while working on their research. At one point, they considered giving up entirely. However, they never forgot how their adviser encouraged them to persist. "*Pero lahat ng iyon ay aking nilabanan*" (*But I fought through all of it*), the teacher emphasized, highlighting their determination to achieve the highest academic distinction. Meanwhile, Teacher 1 noted that their perspective and understanding of various matters had broadened as a result of their experiences.

The **professional transformation** of the teacher-participants emerged through self-reflection. Both Teacher 2 and Teacher 10 realized the importance of pursuing further studies at the postgraduate level to expand their knowledge and skills.

At this stage of their career, Teacher 2 has been able to apply their graduate school research output in practice. They mentioned that the intervention they developed—after identifying students' reading weaknesses through the ORVT-Phil-IRI assessment—is now actively in use and proving beneficial. Similarly, Teacher 4, having completed their postgraduate studies, was inspired to conduct research related to Filipino and continue publishing research articles.

Teacher 7, on the other hand, found the courage to deepen their study of the country's culture to help enrich and intellectualize the Filipino language.

Teacher 8's reflections and transformation focused on their classroom experience. For them, when it comes to research, students should experience the research process firsthand,

reinforcing the importance of integrating research into the learning environment.

Author or Writer. The transformation of the participants in their role as writers is closely tied to their **professional transformation**.

Teacher 1 experienced a shift in belief after reflecting on their knowledge and skills, becoming more critical and cautious in their writing. It can be recalled that they previously mentioned how this was one of the key competencies they developed during their graduate studies. Similarly, Teacher 7 realized that their writing skills had significantly improved, especially as they continued to write literary works such as essays, short stories, and poetry, which they shared on social media. This platform allowed them to discover and further cultivate their creative thinking skills.

Thus, as **authors or writers**, the participants' transformation is mainly **professional**. Their perspective shifted towards being more critical and meticulous in writing. Additionally, their writing was no longer confined to traditional spaces, as social media became a platform for continuing their literary pursuits.

Institution/School Administrator. In their role as institution or school administrators, the participants developed both **Personal Transformation** and **Professional Transformation**.

Regarding **personal transformation**, Teacher 1 expressed that their understanding and empathy for others had broadened. In their capacity as a coordinator, they realized that not everyone shares the same characteristics. Meanwhile, Teacher 2 demonstrated respect for senior or more experienced educators. Despite holding an administrative role, they still acknowledged the expertise of those who had been in the teaching profession longer.

The participants' professional transformation was also analyzed. Teacher 2 realized that being a coordinator was a privilege, stating, "mora baya pod ug maka-proud nga morag ikaw gisaligan so meaning naa kay edge sa uban". [It somehow

feels rewarding and makes me proud because it means I am trusted, which gives me an edge over others.] For Teacher 1, they served as both a coordinator and mentor to newly hired teachers in their school. Both considered it an honor to be entrusted with such a responsibility.

According to Ellis et al., the School21 program values students who will thrive in the 21st century. These students need 21st-century teachers—trainers and educators, project designers, subject specialists, and language teachers. These teachers serve as partners and architects of learning, critical thinkers who continue to grow through extensive reading, observation, and unlocking students' potential.

Thus, personal transformation in their role as administrators is evident in their expanded understanding and empathy for others, as well as their respect for senior colleagues. Meanwhile, professional transformation is reflected in their realization that being a coordinator is a privilege and in their appreciation of their role in mentoring new teachers.

Disorientation. The **disorienting dilemma** is the core of transformative learning. And this can be summed up in the journey of these graduates: Teacher 1 realized their lack of self-confidence, which led to missed opportunities for professional growth in the situation they shared. For Teacher 3, the unexpected additional workload was overwhelming, as it was not part of their initial expectations. They even mentioned becoming a “jack-of-all-trades” due to the nature of the education system they were part of. Meanwhile, Teacher 8 experienced professional disorientation during their teaching assignment in a rural town in Bohol.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Overall, this study can be considered an “a-ha moment” or an awakening for the researcher regarding the transformation brought about by the learning journey of the participants who completed their Master of Arts in Teaching Filipino at two universities in the province of Bohol. The knowledge and skills they acquired from graduate school were beneficial. However, certain new insights and competencies prompted them to revisit

what they had learned, leading to changes in how they fulfilled their roles as teachers, community members, researchers, and authors or writers. On the other hand, some participants expressed incidental transformations arising from their experiences of disorientation. While these experiences heightened their awareness of the realities of their profession and other responsibilities, they still needed a space to express their concerns, anxieties, and perspectives.

It is recommended that a strong association of Filipino language specialists be established at the graduate school level, connections with national organizations of Filipino educators be fostered, and collaborative research across various schools and universities be promoted to strengthen and guide the professional and personal transformation of teachers.

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